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Abstract: This article provides information about the development, role and origin of mass media in our society.

Key words: new media, technology, information, journalism, society, internet, development, public information.

New media are communication technologies that enable or enhance interaction between users as well as interaction between users and content. In the middle of the 1990s, the phrase "new media" became widely used as part of a sales pitch for the influx of interactive CD-ROMs for entertainment and education. The new media technologies, sometimes known as Web 2.0, include a wide range of web-related communication tools such as blogs, wikis, online social networking, virtual worlds, and other social media platforms.

The phrase "new media" refers to computational media that share material online and through computers. New media inspire new ways of thinking about older media. Media do not replace one another in a clear, linear succession, instead evolving in a more complicated network of interconnected feedback loops.

Since the beginning of mankind, information, regardless of its type and content, has been of primary importance in his life, and the demand for information has not lost its relevance even today. Changing times and development have only changed the type of media. Periodicity, relevance and speed have kept pace with the development of journalism. Initially, information in oral form was widespread, but later it was transferred to written forms. Over time, books, newspapers, radio, television and the Internet gradually developed. It is not for nothing that futurologists call the new century the "Information Age". Because now it has become much easier and convenient to do the work that is difficult to do even with large armies or powerful weapons through information. That is why today's struggles are taking place fiercely in "ideological landfills".

Today, almost all experts repeat the idea that "The owner of information rules the world." It is true that this word has also become "fashionable". However, in the 15th century, Alisher Navoi, a great thinker and the sultan of words, skillfully explained this

process in his poems beginning with "Agar ogoh sen...". And the mass media is the protagonist in presenting the status of "royalty" to the centralized big powers. From this point of view, any type of mass media forms and develops the consciousness, worldview, thinking, and generally the spiritual world of society members. Today, choosing the impartial information we need from the flow of information that surrounds us requires deep thinking and deep thinking. As an important element in raising the morale of society, media workers need to be sharper, more impartial and faster than ever. After all, social relations are closely connected with the development of society, first of all, with the development of mass media. In particular, let's take the online world, which is the most popular means of information dissemination today. In a powerful information space, the use of the Internet is increasing, and it has become more convenient for the average reader to get information from the Internet than from television, newspapers, or radio. Consequently, internet journalism has become the newest and most convenient means of information distribution and has its place and influence in mass media. The availability of access to the Internet at any time, anywhere and under any conditions using a mobile phone has dramatically increased the speed of its use. Especially today, we have reached the stage where young people cannot imagine their life without the Internet. So, the worldview of the audience using it is formed depending on the potential, culture, and knowledge level of network journalists. Since the spiritual development of the society depends on the mass media, it is necessary for today's journalist to master the skill of conveying information based on our Uzbek talents, preserving the characteristics of our nation.

In the conditions of globalization, the ability to fully form the national information space, information immunity among our citizens and the ability to form opposing opinions by creating mechanisms against foreign ideas are not only important issues aligned with the strategic interests of states. Uzbekistan, maybe any country in the world. For example, the book "Issues of genre and skill in print media" says: "News serves not only the development of the country and society, but also the development of the international community. gains international importance. For example, the awareness of the peoples of the world about news in science accelerates development, that is, as a result of discoveries and inventions, people begin to try to understand the world and identity. Being aware of economic and political news affects relations. between countries, leading to the development.

Today's mass media is increasingly adapting to consumer demands, not only to fulfill their wishes, but also to maintain the level of journalism that strives from complexity to simplicity every minute, to operate on the basis of the golden balance,

and to masterfully subjugate the audience to this rule. Uzbek media is an urgent task ahead. After all, directing and managing young people who are the owners of tomorrow, giving them direction, mobilizing them towards good goals, and raising their spirituality to a high level are among the problems facing the industry.

In conclusion, it should be said that in a situation where the role and importance of information in human life is changing completely, the development of proposals and conclusions about the full-fledged activity of mass media in serving the interests of the nation and the state and forming the consciousness of citizens is today in front of science. is among the problems waiting to be solved. In particular, the influence of mass media on people's minds and thinking is not only expanding, but is becoming so subtle that it is impossible to ignore any issue or problem in the field of mass media. After all, at the same time that information is primarily a source of knowledge, it is also a source of spirituality, enlightenment, ethics and, of course, political views. Therefore, the mass media, which is a force influencing the development of our society and the spiritual world of our citizens, needs to be polished and is worthy of research today more than ever.

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